

Receiver-driven routing for community mesh networks

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Abstract—Community wireless mesh networks are decentralized and cooperative structures with participation rules that define their freedom, openness and neutrality. The operation of these networks require routing algorithms that may impose additional unnecessary technical restrictions in the determination of routes that can restrict the freedom of community users. We propose a receiver-driven discretionary routing mechanism where each receiver can freely specify delivery objectives and remain compatible with the collaborative approach of community networks. Each node has a unique identifier and can announce the description of its offer and also the description of its routing policy with preferences to deliver traffic to it. BMX6 provides a “hash-based profile propagation mechanism” to disseminate these descriptions. This receiver-driven routing can be applied to express preferences for desirable nodes and paths, or to restrict traffic to trusted nodes enabling trust and security aware routing. We validate our contributions with a proof of concept implementation of key concepts, developed as an extension of the BMX6 routing protocol, that confirms its feasibility and scalability.

Index Terms—routing; community mesh networks; metric policies; trust; security;

I. INTRODUCTION

Community wireless mesh networks are decentralized and cooperative structures that grow organically in communities where network nodes are owned, contributed and administered by its members.

Routing in community wireless mesh networks is based on the principle of cooperation among the participants. These communities usually have participation rules as a membership license or peering agreement that define their freedom, openness and neutrality. The implementation of these networks require technical agreements for data transit among any pair of network nodes. That includes the use of a specific routing protocol where nodes learn and inform about the state of the network and update their own routing tables.

Current routing protocols, including OLSR [14], BATMAN [12] and many others [10] are based on running a common algorithm and share a common set of metrics to determine the routes for all network nodes. However, the participants in the network and its diverse infrastructure should not impose technical restrictions limiting the freedom of the community users beyond the accepted participation rules. The main challenge is

to provide routing mechanisms that can respect and enhance community cooperation and individual freedom.

In this work we present a receiver-driven discretionary routing mechanism where each receiver can freely specify delivery objectives and remaining compatible with the collaborative approach of community networks. The mechanism relies in that packet forwarding in IP networks is destination driven. Therefore it is equivalent to assuming the receiver owns packets sent to them and then it should decide about its routing. Each participant in the community network, as a potential receiver, should have the means to identify itself, and specify its offer in terms of resources and implications or limitations. Being aware of the profiles of all nodes in a network, each participant could select which available resources he wants to accept for the forwarding of its own traffic.

Receiver-driven routing can be used by receivers to express preference for nodes and paths with desired characteristics. A receiver of interactive traffic may prefer to route traffic exclusively or preferably through nodes with a track record of low latency or high availability. Another key application is to enable trust-driven routing. A receiver may want to get any object only through trusted nodes or avoid untrusted nodes that may affect his data such as for non-encrypted traffic.

We have experimented with the ideas as part of BMX6 [13], where each node can have a descriptive profile, and a global unique and non-ambiguous hash as identifier. BMX6 provides a “hash-based profile propagation mechanism” to disseminate profile information between nodes of a community network. Nodes can use this information to construct and announce its routing policy to any sender. Building on this our receiver-driven routing mechanism has been tested.

The rest of the paper presents the design of receiver-driven routing. We validate our contributions with a proof of concept implementation of the main idea.

II. RECEIVER-DRIVEN ROUTING

A. Assumptions and Design Considerations

Routing in community networks is based on the principle of cooperation. To conceptually maximize the opportunities (in terms of network resources) for cooperation despite the typical infrastructure and user heterogeneity of community networks,

a principal cooperation should not depend on specific mandatory rules or policies.

Therefore, instead of enforcing the same behavior to all components of a community network by employing specific prevention mechanisms, the participation rules should be open and only demanding a formal (and authenticated) announcement/publication of offered resources and implications. Users should be empowered to dynamically select the set of published resources and acceptable implications as needed for their individual objectives.

Practically, any infrastructure owner willing to (at least) partially share his resources should be provided with means to identify himself and specify his offer and the implications or limitations that he associates with this offer in a node-specific profile. As an example such profile, providing a list of resources and implications may include the following “offer” attributes:

- Routing topology and reachability information (link-local and end-to-end path metrics via this node to others).
- Supported metric functions (e.g. ETX, ETT, hop-count).
- Locally reachable networks: locally offered gateway and proxy services.
- Traffic shaping implications: identity information (eg: this node is owned by *X*, you may not trust me).
- Responsibility information (this node is managed by *Y* who certified that its operating according to policy *Z*).

Being aware of the profiles of all nodes in a network, each community network user (node’s routing protocol) could select from the available resources those he wants to accept for the forwarding of his own traffic (by adding forwarding requirements to his own profile). A list of typical forwarding requirements could be:

- End-to-end path establishment (route selection) according to ETT metric function.
- Only via nodes that do not apply traffic shaping.
- Only using gateway services of node *A* and *B*.
- Only route my traffic via nodes owned or managed by *C*.

In summary, enhanced trust and security is achieved by letting nodes waive existing resources.

B. Principles and Proposed Mechanism

To enable the above given objectives and use cases we propose a (i) “receiver-driven routing mechanism” that leverages (builds on top of) a (ii) “hash-based description propagation mechanism” (as in BMX6) to disseminate profile information between nodes of a community network.

Receiver-driven routing is targeted to enable this user-individual routing with respect to available network resources and each user’s forwarding requirements.

Typically, in IP networks, the packet forwarding is destination driven (each node along the path is consulting its routing tables for the destination address of a packet for forwarding it) and, unless doing (i) source routing or (ii) having an individual routing table for each potential source node, the sender of any packet loses control about the further routing once it is sent

out. As an example, two different senders sending packets to the same destination can not enforce a different forwarding policy because the next hop will only consider the destination address (not the source) for identifying the next hop.

Our proposal is based on the assumption that the owner of a packet is the receiver of it (*not* the sender). We think that is a fair assumption, because the consequences are similar to e.g. the (good old) postal system where, once an envelope is dropped into the post box and sufficiently postpaid, the envelope becomes the property of the receiver.

To enable the distributed application of node-individual forwarding policies we associate routing update messages with a specification of the destination node’s forwarding requirements. All other nodes are requested to use this specification when identifying the next hop and configure the routing table entry towards this destination address respectively.

A consequence of this approach is that if intermediate nodes are following the forwarding policies defined by the destination node, then the destination node’s traffic will only be forwarded according to its rules. Further, if the destination node is able to specify a set of trustable nodes (nodes that indeed obey the destination nodes specifications), then, once a data packet is routed via any of the trusted nodes it will never leave the set of trusted nodes along its path until it is delivered to its final destination.

Following this approach an enhanced level of trust and security can be achieved simply by allowing nodes to waive out some offered resources for the forwarding of their data (for example because they do not trust them). Maybe the resulting end-to-end paths are less optimal or even not possible (compared to using all offered links and nodes of the network). However, we believe that is similar to real-life security. Individually I may decide not to cross dark forests at night and sometimes I must accept a long way around or even that I can not reach the guy living in the middle of a forest.

A more concrete algorithm supporting this approach can operate as follows:

- Each node owns a public and private key pair.
- The hash of the public key is used for non-ambiguous identification of the node.
- Each node creates a description of itself including its public key, offered resources and implications, and forwarding requirements (see above). Further, the node profiles is signed by with its private key.
- Each node description and the corresponding signatures are propagated over the network and unambiguously referenced using the hash of the overall profile (*not* the public key hash).
- Like any Destination Sequenced Distant Vector Protocol, each node periodically propagates routing update messages containing a sequence number, the metric value, and (instead of a destination address) a reference to the originator node’s profile (e.g. the profile hash).
- When node *A* receives a routing update originated by node *D* via neighbor *N* then:
 - *A* looks up the referenced profile from *D* and checks

whether N is in the set of nodes that D trusts and that N fulfills the forwarding requirements defined by D .

- If this is the case, then N is a potential next hop for forwarding traffic towards D . If not, then the routing update is silently dropped.
- If N is a potential next hop for D 's traffic, then A uses the metric function defined via D 's profile to calculate the current metric value to reach D and uses this value for ranking between alternative next hops towards D .
- A configures the routing table towards the addresses defined in D 's profile via the best ranking neighbor.

C. Technical Protocol Requirements

Based on the above presented mechanism a number of protocol requirements can be identified. In the following we summarize these requirements and point to existing concepts and solutions that can be used for an implementation and validation of our ideas.

Although our proposed mechanisms may (with conceptual adaptations) be applicable also to link-state based routing protocols we believe that (proactive) table-driven destination-sequenced distance-vector based protocol will fit best to allow an efficient and loop-free operation of our proposal. The main argument here is that for link-state based protocols our approach would require a continuous (re-)calculation of the complete end-to-end path between all nodes of a network and this for each node's forwarding-requirement policy. On the other hand, for distance-vector based protocols the calculation must only be done for the next hop towards each originator and each with respect to the originator's policy specification.

An information propagation mechanism for disseminating node profiles in the network is needed that satisfies the following requirements:

- The mechanism must be capable to deal with so called opportunistic networks [9]. This is important to ensure that node's profile information becomes available as soon as possible and despite the existence of unstable and temporary broken links or even disconnected fractions of the network because the previous availability of this information is a prerequisite for other nodes to instantly resolve and process node identities, attributes, and routing updates.
- Independent propagation of profile information and routing updates. This is needed since routing updates rely on previous local availability of the originator's profile.
- Referencing: To allow for an efficient (in terms of traffic and computational overhead) association of frequent and periodic routing updates with the originator's profile information it must be possible to non-ambiguously reference originator profiles with comparatively compact profile identifiers (e.g. by using the hash of a profile).
- Dynamic profile updates and continuous synchronization of this information with other nodes is required to, on the one hand, let nodes change their resource offers and

implication announcements and, on the other hand, let nodes adapt their forwarding-policy specification to either changed resource availability or new traffic, security, or trust requirements.

- Originator identification, authentication, information integrity, and non-repudiation: needed to provide receiving nodes with means to validate the authenticity and integrity of profile information originated by other nodes.
- Versioning: Profile information and referencing must allow the receivers to distinguish old from newer versions from the same originator. This is needed to ensure that processing of routing update messages can always be associated with the latest valid profile of the originating node.

To support the traffic forwarding only via trusted nodes the routing protocol must allow dynamic white/black listing of particular intermediate nodes that could be used or must be ignored during the selection process of potential next-hop nodes for the routing. Further, the routing protocol must be capable to create and process a syntax for specifying and communicating those trusted nodes.

Scalable verification of authenticity and credibility. Since the users (node administrators) of a large community network can hardly know and maintain comprehensive black or white lists, classifying all nodes of the network into trustable or not, mechanisms are needed to let users rely on already existing chains or networks of trust. A natural candidate for this problem would be given by what is known as a *web of trust*.

The routing protocol must allow the dynamic (re-)configuration of metric functions and parametrizations. Although existing routing protocol implementations exist that allow the usage of different metric functions (for example the OLSR implementation of OLSR.org [20] allows this via metric plugins and Babel [11] comes with separate implementations for different metric flavors), to the best of our knowledge none of the existing open routing protocol implementations are currently able to change this behavior on the fly. However, this is needed to dynamically apply node-individual metric specifications without restarting the network. Further, the routing protocol must be capable to create and process a syntax for specifying metric functions and parametrizations as needed to express and communicate the desired route-selection behavior to other nodes.

Mechanisms for secure communication (authentication, integrity, confidentiality, non-repudiation) with neighboring (potential next hops) nodes. This is necessary to ensure that protocol data is indeed exchanged between authentic neighboring nodes and that to-be forwarded data is forwarded via the intended next-hop. To support this, existing security solutions like IPSEC [21] can be used.

Suite of cryptographic tools for calculation of security attributes. A variety of open libraries exist for solving the required cryptographic mechanisms using standardized APIs. In particular we are focusing the openssl [22] API which is also supported by CyaSSL [23], a very lightweight and efficient SSL library for embedded devices.

III. VALIDATION AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

As a proof of concept, key mechanisms of our proposal have been implemented based on existing work of the BMX6 routing protocol and validated via an emulation of typical scenarios. In the following we quickly summarize the requirements already provided by the BMX6 routing protocol and the functional extensions that have been made. Following the description of the methodology and tested scenario we summarize performance and scalability observations in terms of computation and communication overhead.

A. Leveraged BMX6 mechanisms

Our current implementation builds on top of the BMX6 routing protocol [13] because its concepts and implementation [24] already leverage and provide key mechanisms for the requirements as discussed in Section II-C. In particular, it is a proactive, table-driven routing protocol for mesh networks, leveraging concepts of destination-sequenced, distance-vector protocols. Further, the current implementation is fully open-source (GPL licensed), and actively maintained and used (for example in various Guifi.net [26] community-network clouds and fully integrated in community network node-system distributions like qMp [25]). BMX6 also provides an opportunistic-network tolerant information propagation mechanisms operating independently of the routing-update mechanism and allowing efficient referencing of descriptions via hashes and individual identifiers, continuous and dynamic description updates, and versioning. Further, the mechanism allows to piggyback arbitrary additional content via description extensions and propagate them with the rest of the node's profile in a network. This feature has already been used by third-party applications to disseminate detailed topology information for visualization purposes, service announcements, and instant messaging data. In the scope of this proposal, this feature will be used for propagating white/black lists of trustable nodes, security attributes (public keys, description signatures, trust chains), and metric-functions and policies.

B. Extensions toward Receiver/Preference Driven Routing

Our current extensions allow the concurrent application of different metric functions (including hop-count and expected transmit count (ETX) [17], a rudimentary expected transmit time (ETT) metric [16], and transmit quality (TQ), a multiplicative routing metric proposed by the B.A.T.M.A.N. [18] protocol considering the transmit qualities of asymmetric links and respecting different link characteristics.

To achieve this we have defined a metric description syntax and added description extensions for the metrics plugin of BMX6 in a way that a destination node can select between several base metric functions and customize them with general and base-function specific parameters. For example it is possible to define the sliding window size for best next-hop ranking when averaging the metric values reviewed via recent routing updates (originator messages in BMX6 terminology). A dynamic description update including the current metrics specification is triggered whenever the configuration

is changed and instantly processed and applied by receiving nodes when selecting the best hop neighbor for a particular destination node.

C. Validation via proof-of-concept

In order to validate the distributed application of node-individual metric functions, our implementation has been deployed and executed over a emulated network environment [15] and resulting forwarding paths between nodes specifying different metric functions for the routing of their traffic have been compared using the ping record route option. In particular, a purely hop-count based metric function was compared with the multiplicative and link-asymmetry aware TQ metric function. To stimulate the functions for selecting different routes, a simple ring topology with a total of 5 nodes (e.g.: A-B-C-D-E-A) but highly asymmetric link characteristics between neighboring nodes has been set up. The link asymmetries were configured that no loss occurs for packets transmitted from any node to its right neighbor but 20% of packet loss occurs in the opposite direction (to a node's left-hand neighbor). Initially, all nodes were configured with the hop-count metric and as expected, any resulting path traversed at most two hops. After dynamically reconfiguring node E for selecting the TQ metric function all traffic meant for node E was routed clockwise along the ring topology. In particular, a ping record route from A to A's left-hand neighboring node E showed that the packet was routed along A-B-C-D-E while a ping from A to D continued to traverse (in the opposite direction) along A-E-D.

In summary, the tested scenario proves the key idea for receiver-driven routing being the feasibility to let destination nodes specify and achieve the distributed application of specific forwarding policies. Next we will extend our implementation with the propagation and handling of white/black lists of trustable nodes and security attributes.

D. Performance and scalability

The discussion of performance impacts is separated into typical operational phases of a routing protocol, namely the discovery phase (propagation and processing of node descriptions), the maintenance phase (propagation and processing of routing updates), and the forwarding phase (forwarding according to the current state of the routing table).

During the discovery phase, no measurable impact could be observed for the computational overhead caused by the processing of our description extensions and only a marginal impact could be measured for the related protocol-traffic overhead due to its extended size for propagating the to-be-used metric functions and parametrizations. In fact our metric extensions increases the existing description by only 16 bytes which must be compared to the overall description size ranging (depending on amount of announced networks and other attributes and services) between 110 and several 100 bytes. Further, it should be noted that the discovery phase (although it could repeat due to the dynamical re-configuration capabilities of the protocol) only lasts few seconds and is

supposed to occur only due to manual reconfigurations of a node which can be expected to occur rather seldom.

For the outstanding validation of verifying authenticity and integrity of description updates, we indeed expect a significant performance hit. However, some preliminary tests using the Linux OpenWRT embedded OS and the OpenSSL Speedtest on a typical device like the ubiquity RouterStation (AR7161 - MIPS 24K CPU running at 680MHz) showed the feasibility of calculating a SHA1 hash for up to 8192 size blocks in less than 0.3 ms and signing/verifying data with 264 versus 3116 bps using a 512 bit RSA key pair (and signing/verifying with 50 versus 1040 bps using 1024 bit RSA key). Extrapolating these measurements for signing a BMX6 description of up to 1K means that a node (based on this hardware and *not* using any hardware-based crypto acceleration) would need less than 1.7 seconds for hashing its own description and RSA512-based signing of the resulting 160 bit SHA1 hash (required only during startup and reconfiguration scenarios) and would require “only” 50 ms for hashing and verifying other nodes descriptions (which is required only for casual description update of other nodes).

Related to the maintenance phase, no impact was expected nor observed for the traffic overhead because none of the periodic messages needed for monitoring (probing) and for propagating link and end-to-end path variations are affected. In particular the routing update messages (originator messages) remain unchanged and are only processed differently. The impact, caused by the modified processing of destination-specific metric functions and differing only in using a function pointer instead of a hardcoded function, again results in non-measurable performance penalties. In fact, the only (still-hardly) measurable impact could be assigned to the overhead caused by specific functions simply because in our implementation different metric algorithms require different amounts of normalizations, multiplications, divisions, or even square-root calculations. However, this affect would be the same when supporting only a unique and hard-coded function.

It should be noted that the marginal impact of the maintenance phase can be considered most relevant for the overall overhead and scalability of a routing protocol because in large networks, the great majority of traffic and related processing is caused by the continuous propagation and processing of periodic routing updates. For example an emulation of BMX6, operating a 50/100/150/200 nodes, stable, grid-like topology with 4 neighbors for each non-edge node showed the averaged fraction of protocol traffic related to OGM advertisements increasing to 55/70/75/80 percent (total protocol traffic per node 125/180/240/270 Bps) respectively.

However, a slightly increased performance penalty is expected for the requirement of secure communication of protocol data with neighboring nodes. But again, this overhead will be caused by the Linux kernel and the employed IPSEC implementation since the validation, calculation, and configuration of security attributes for the IPSEC stack will be done as an outcome of the discovery phase. Recent hardware measurements published in the OpenWRT wiki [28] report that

reasonable IPSEC-encrypted throughput performance can be achieved with current embedded devices. For example using the AES256 cipher, encryption at up to 37Mbps is possible using a (AR7161) MIPS 24K CPU running at 680MHz. This is enough to secure the comparatively small protocol traffic load between neighboring nodes (less than 3Kbps for a 200-nodes network) and even reasonable to encrypt user data.

For the forwarding phase no additional overhead was expected nor measured. This is because the protocol only configures the kernel’s routing table (as the outcome of the maintenance phase) and relies on the lookup of routing table entries for each packet as performed by the linux kernel.

IV. RELATED WORK

Related to reliability (security) and responsibility: [1] provides interesting numbers on the awareness and counter measurements on routing security in the internet. [2] provides a survey on security issues in mesh networks presenting specific approaches to address secure/reliable routing in mesh networks. This work is aligned with these.

Related to discretionary routing and heterogeneous objectives, very little attention has been devoted to the simultaneous support of heterogeneous (routing) objectives in collaborative networking.

The pico-peering agreement [19] provides a minimum baseline template for defining an abstract interoperability agreement between owners of individual network nodes but leaves technical solutions to achieve an efficient multi-hop networking completely open. The guifi.net licence [26] is more specific in terms of expected conduct but often softens the main statement with exceptions (Section 3.2. “Whenever possible, the general criteria must be”). Also it demands that “network management criteria must be published” but leaves open how protocols could automatically consider the published criteria of a specific nodes for routing.

In terms of technical solutions, [3] presents a routing-protocol coordinator that allows nodes to communicate with each other even though they are equipped with heterogeneous routing protocols. [4] approaches the interoperability problem in WMNs by proposing a cross-layer heterogeneous routing protocol.

To some extent, current routing protocol implementations have solved specific issues of the dilemma. For example OLSR [14], BMX6 [13] have integrated support to let each mesh-nodes select an individual gateway node to the internet. [13] also allows concurrent usage of individual (per-node) routing algorithms and metrics. The community projects [25], [27] enabled multi-stack routing, using address-range separation and policy routing to allow simultaneous usage of different routing protocols.

To the best of our knowledge, no work has been published yet that aims to combine the two directions of reliability and discretionary routing policies into a coherent framework.

V. CONCLUSION

We have presented a receiver-driven discretionary routing mechanism for community networks where each receiver can

freely specify delivery objectives and remaining compatible with the collaborative approach of community networks. This routing mechanism can be applied to express preferences for desirable nodes and paths, or to restrict traffic to trusted nodes enabling trust and security aware routing. A proof-of-concept implementation of key concepts, developed as an extension of the BMX6 routing protocol, confirms its feasibility and scalability.

In future work we plan to develop a complete implementation of the routing mechanism over BMX6, including syntax, authentication, signature and engine for policy specifications, definition of the bootstrapping procedure. In particular we are interested in further exploring the characteristics and limits of the protocol over larger and more realistic scenarios with the support of the Community-Lab [29] testbed.

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